

A Prospective Observational Study on Relationship Between Osteoarthritis and Body Mass Index

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ABSTRACT

Background: Osteoarthritis (OA) is a chronic joint disease-causing pain, stiffness, and functional limitations, primarily affecting weight-bearing joints. Obesity and increased Body Mass Index (BMI) contribute significantly to OA risk due to mechanical stress and inflammation. **Objective:** This study examines the association between BMI and OA, evaluates risk factors, assesses pain severity, and explores the impact of weight management on disease progression. **Methodology:** A prospective observational study was conducted at Sri Raghavendra Multi-Specialty Hospital, Narasaraopet, over six months (August 2024 - January 2025), including 100 OA patients. Data were collected using the Western Ontario and McMaster Universities Osteoarthritis Index (WOMAC) for pain severity and the Kellgren-Lawrence grading scale for radiographic assessment. BMI was recorded at baseline and follow-up, with statistical analysis applied to assess correlations. **Results:** The study included 56% females and 44% males, with OA most common in individuals aged 51-60 years (33%). Daily wage workers (31%) and housewives (24%) had higher prevalence, likely due to occupational strain. Hypertension (29%) and diabetes (18%) were common comorbidities. At baseline, 64% were overweight, and 27% were classified as Obese Class I. Lifestyle modifications resulted in slight BMI reductions and pain improvement. **Conclusion:** Higher BMI is strongly associated with OA severity. Weight management and lifestyle changes can alleviate symptoms, highlighting the importance of early intervention.

Keywords: Osteoarthritis, Body Mass Index, Obesity, Pain Severity, Risk Factors, Lifestyle Modification..

INTRODUCTION

Background on Osteoarthritis (OA):

Osteoarthritis (OA) is one of the major problems with significant morbidity. It is a chronic degenerative disorder of bone joints characterized by loss of articular cartilage, hypertrophy of bone at the margins and subchondral sclerosis. Customarily it affects joints of extremities and spine particularly of weight bearing joints. Osteoarthritis (OA) of knee is a common cause of pain and disability especially in older adults [1]. X-ray is the first-choice imaging modality in the diagnosis of KOA. In general, anteroposterior and lateral radiographs of the knee joint, particularly the weight-bearing views, are

required for the comparison of bilateral knee joints [2].

At present, osteoarthritis (OA) continues to be a significant public health problem globally. As it is a highly prevalent and disabling disease, it imposes a tremendous disease burden. One study reported a prevalence of 595 million individuals affected by osteoarthritis globally in 2020, accounting for 7.6% of the total population, with osteoarthritis being identified as the seventh leading cause of years lived with disability for those aged 70 years and older. The projected trends from 2021 to 2050 suggest that the disease burden of OA will continue to grow, posing a challenge for healthcare systems worldwide [3].

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Role of Body Mass Index (BMI) in OA:

The body mass index (BMI) is the metric currently in use for defining anthropometric height/weight characteristics in adults and for classifying (categorizing) them into groups. The common interpretation is that it represents an index of an individual's fatness. It also is widely used as a risk factor for the development of or the prevalence of several health issues such as hypertension, diabetes, hypercholesterolemia, osteoarthritis and other conditions [4].

The association between obesity and the incidence and prevalence of osteoarthritis has been well established. High body mass index is a risk factor for knee osteoarthritis. A previous study reported a 35% increase in knee osteoarthritis (KOA) risk with every 5-unit increase in body mass index [5]. The connection between obesity and osteoarthritis is attributed to not only mechanical loading and "wear-and-tear" at the cartilage surface, but also metabolic and inflammatory mediators, specifically degradative enzymes and adipose tissue- derived cytokines (known as adipokines). Some adipokines, such as leptin, adiponectin, and lipocalin 2, among others, induce production of inflammatory adiponectin, and lipocalin 2, among others, induce production of inflammatory cytokines, including tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α), interleukin-6 (IL-6) thus resulting in cartilage matrix damage and subchondral bone remodeling [6].

Rationale for the Study:

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a major cause of disability worldwide, affecting millions of individuals, particularly the elderly [7]. Obesity and increased Body Mass Index (BMI) have been strongly associated with OA development and progression due to mechanical stress and inflammatory responses [8]. While multiple studies have identified obesity as a risk factor for OA, limited prospective research has examined the direct correlation between BMI, pain severity, and disease progression using validated clinical scoring systems [9]. Understanding this relationship is crucial for developing targeted interventions aimed at reducing the burden of OA through weight management strategies [10].

Objectives:

- To check the BMI in patients suffering from osteoarthritis.
- To assess any associated risk factors that can cause osteoarthritis.
- To assess the pain in patients with osteoarthritis.
- To improve patients BMI by life style modifications (weight reduction).

METHODOLOGY

The methodology section describes in detail all the materials that have been used to conduct a study well as the procedures that are under taken.

Study design: A hospital based Prospective Observational Study.

Study site: This study was conducted at Sri Raghavendra Multi Specialty Hospital, Narasaraopet.

Study period: The study is proposed to conduct in a period of 6 months.

Sample size: A total of 100 subjects who were clinically and radiologically diagnosed with osteoarthritis were included in the study. Those who fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria were selected for the study.

Study criteria: The study will be carried out by considering the following criteria:

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients suffering with osteoarthritis diagnosed either clinically or radiologically were included.
- Patients of age 30-80 years were included.
- Patients with comorbidities were also included.
- Patients of both the genders.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients found to be suffering from other joint related conditions were excluded.
- Patients age >80 years were excluded.

- Patients with trauma, acute infections were excluded.

Table 1 shows gender wise distribution. Demographic data reveals that females are more when compared to males.

RESULTS

Table.1: Distribution based on gender

S. No	Gender	No. of Patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Female	56	56%
2	Male	44	44%

Fig.1: Distribution based on gender

Table 2 shows age wise distribution. This data reveals that the patient age in between 51-60 were

found to be high followed by 41-50, 61-70 age group

Table.2: Distribution based on age

S. No	Age Group	No. of Patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	21-30	2	2
2	31-40	8	8
3	41-50	31	31
4	51-60	33	33
5	61-70	21	21
6	71-80	5	5

Fig.2: Distribution based on age

Table 3 shows the occupation analysis. This data reveals that the daily wage workers were found to be high, followed by housewives and farmers.

Table.3: Distribution based on occupation

S. No	Occupation	No. of patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Housewife	24	24
2	Daily wage worker	31	31
3	Farmer	15	15
4	Teacher	10	10
5	Conductor	5	5
6	Journalist	1	1
7	Nurse	1	1
8	Driver	2	2
9	Worker	2	2
10	Tailor	5	5
11	Police	1	1
12	Attender	3	3

Fig.3: Distribution based on occupation

Table 4 shows the comorbidities analysis. This data reveals that the hypertensive patients were found to be high followed by diabetes mellitus

Table.4: Distribution based on comorbidities

S. No	Comorbidities	No. of patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Depression	1	1
2	DM	18	18
3	DM, Hypothyroidism	1	1
4	HTN	29	29
5	HTN, DM	13	13
6	HTN, DM, Hyperlipidemia	1	1
7	HTN, DM, IHD	1	1
8	HTN, Hypothyroidism	4	4
9	Hyperlipidemia	1	1
10	Hyperlipidemia, HTN	2	2
11	Hypothyroidism	1	1
12	PCOD	1	1
13	None	27	27

Fig.4: Distribution based on comorbidities

Table 5 shows the BMI category analysis at visit. This data reveals that the patient having BMI (25-29.9kg/ m²) were found to be high followed by (30-34.9kg/ m²).

Table.5: Distribution based on BMI at visit

S. No	BMI category	No. of patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Normal	4	4
2	Over weight	64	64
3	Obese class-I	27	27
4	Obese class-II	5	5

Fig.4: Distribution based on BMI at visit

Table 6 shows the BMI category analysis at review. This data reveals that the patient having

BMI (25-29.9kg/ m²) were found to be high followed by (30-34.9kg/ m²).

Table.6: Distribution based on BMI at review

S. No	BMI category	No. of patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Normal	5	5
2	Over weight	69	69
3	Obese class-I	21	21
4	Obese class-II	5	5

Fig.5: Distribution based on BMI at review

Table 7 shows comparison of BMI at visit and at review. In both the cases the individuals having BMI ranges from 25-29.9kg/m² had the highest incidence at visit 64% (n=64) at review 69% (n=69).

Table.7: Distribution based on BMI at visit and review

S. No	BMI category	No. of patients (n=100) at visit	No. of patients (n=100) at review
1	Normal	4	5
2	Over weight	64	69
3	Obese class-I	27	21
4	Obese class- II	5	5

Figure.7: Distribution based on BMI at visit and review

Table 8 shows WOMAC score category analysis at visit. This data reveals that patients having moderate pain were found to be high followed by severe.

Table.8: Distribution based on WOMAC at visit

S. No	WOMAC score	No. of patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Mild (0-24)	12	12
2	Moderate (25-48)	50	50
3	Severe (49-72)	31	31
4	Extreme (73-96)	7	7

Fig.8: Distribution based on WOMAC at visit

Table 9 shows WOMAC score category analysis at review. This data reveals that patients having

moderate pain were found to be high followed by severe.

Table.9: Distribution based on WOMAC at review

S. No	WOMAC score	No. of patient (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Mild (0-24)	15	15
2	Moderate (25-48)	54	54
3	Severe (49-72)	26	26
4	Extreme (73-96)	5	5

Fig.9: Distribution based on WOMAC at review

Table 10 shows comparison of WOMAC score at visit and at review, in both the cases individuals having WOMAC score: moderate had the highest incidence of pain at visit 50% (n=50) at review 54% (n=54).

Table.10: Distribution based on WOMAC at visit and review

S. No	WOMAC score	No. of Patients (n=100) at visit	No. of patients (n=100) at review
1	Mild (0-24)	12	15
2	Moderate (25-48)	50	54
3	Severe (49-72)	31	26
4	Extreme (73-96)	7	5

Fig.10: Distribution based on WOMAC at visit and review

Table 11 shows distribution based on x-ray grade. individuals with grade-2 X- ray findings had highest incidence of knee osteoarthritis 45% (n=45), followed by grade-3 23% (n=23).

Table.11: Distribution based on X- Ray grading

S. No	X-ray grade	No. of patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Grade-0	1	1
2	Grade-1	16	16
3	Grade-2	45	45
4	Grade-3	23	23
5	Grade-4	6	6
6	Right grade-4, Left grade-2	1	1
7	Right grade-2, Left grade-3	2	2
8	Right grade-4, Left grade-3	2	2
9	Right grade-2, Left grade-1	2	2
10	Right grade-2, Left grade-2	2	2

Fig.11: Distribution based on X- Ray grading

Table 12 shows distribution based on knee affected, individuals with unilateral (right) knee osteoarthritis had the highest incidence 51% (n=51), followed by

unilateral (left) knee osteoarthritis 40% (n=40), bilateral knee osteoarthritis 9% (n=9).

Table.12: Distribution based on knee affected

S. No	Knee affected		No. of patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Unilateral	Right	51	51
		Left	40	40
2	Bilateral		9	9

Fig.12: Distribution based on knee affected

Table13 shows relation between BMI category and WOMAC score at visit and review, the subjects of category over weight had the highest incidence of pain score from WOMAC scale i.e., moderate n=40 at visit and n=44 at review.

Table.13: Relation between BMI and WOMAC score

S. No	BMI Category	WOMAC score							
		Mild (0-24)		Moderate (25-48)		Severe (49-72)		Extreme (73-96)	
		At visit	At review	At visit	At review	At visit	At review	At visit	At review
1	Normal	2	2	1	2	0	0	1	1
2	Over weight	9	11	40	44	11	11	4	3
3	Obese class-I	1	5	7	9	19	7	0	0
4	Obese class-II	0	1	2	1	1	1	2	2

Fig.13: Relation between BMI and WOMAC score

Table 14 shows relation between BMI category and X-ray grading, individuals who are in over weight category had shown the highest incidence of right leg knee osteoarthritis with grade-2 n=21 X-ray grading, followed by left leg with grade-2 n=18.

Table.14: Relation between BMI and X-ray grade

S. No	X- ray grading		BMI category			
			Normal	Over weight	Obese class-I	Obese class-II
1	Grade-0	Right	0	0	0	0
		Left	0	1	0	0
2	Grade-1	Right	0	6	2	1
		Left	2	5	0	0
3	Grade-2	Right	0	21	5	2
		Left	1	18	2	0
4	Grade-3	Right	0	5	9	0
		Left	0	4	7	0
5	Grade-4	Right	0	4	2	1
		Left	1	0	0	1

Fig.14: Relation between BMI and X-ray grade

DISCUSSION

This prospective observational study explores the relationship between osteoarthritis (OA) and Body Mass Index (BMI) among 100 patients at Sri Raghavendra Multi-Specialty Hospital, Narasaraopet, over six months. Using the Kellgren-Lawrence X-ray grading system and the WOMAC index for pain assessment, the study found a higher prevalence of OA in females (56%), with the most affected age group being 51-60 years (33%). Occupational distribution showed the highest prevalence among daily wage workers (31%), followed by housewives (24%) and farmers (15%), highlighting the impact of physically demanding jobs. Comorbidities were common, with hypertension (29%) being the most prevalent. BMI analysis at the initial visit indicated that 64% of patients were overweight, and 27% were in Obese Class I, reinforcing the link between excess weight and OA. Upon review, overweight individuals increased to 69%, while obesity slightly decreased, suggesting potential benefits of lifestyle modifications. X-ray grading showed that Grade 2 OA was most prevalent (45%), and unilateral knee involvement was more common, with 51% having right knee OA.

Pain assessment using the WOMAC score revealed that 50% of patients initially experienced moderate

pain, while 31% had severe pain, with a slight improvement observed at review. The relationship between BMI and WOMAC scores showed that overweight patients had the highest incidence of moderate pain (40% at visit, 44% at review), further supporting the role of BMI in OA severity. Similarly, the correlation between BMI and X-ray grading found that Grade 2 OA was most prevalent in overweight patients, with right knee involvement being more common. These findings emphasize the impact of excess weight on OA progression and pain severity, highlighting the need for weight management in OA treatment strategies.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the strong correlation between BMI and osteoarthritis, showing that excess weight increases mechanical stress on joints, leading to higher pain severity and radiographic changes. The high prevalence of comorbidities like hypertension and diabetes further suggests a metabolic link to osteoarthritis. These findings align with Shetty et al. (2021), reinforcing BMI's role in knee osteoarthritis.

Lifestyle modifications, including weight management and physical activity, led to slight BMI improvements and reduced pain severity, emphasizing the value of early non-pharmacological

interventions. Public health strategies promoting weight control and healthy habits are crucial for osteoarthritis prevention and management. Larger studies with longer follow-ups are needed to assess the long-term impact of BMI reduction on disease progression.

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HOW TO CITE: S. K. Mulla Mobin*, J. N. Suresh Kumar, K. Anirudh Phani Bhargav, D. Sravani, K. Jahnavi, M. Likhitha, S. K. Arif, A Prospective Observational Study on Relationship Between Osteoarthritis and Body Mass Index, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (4), 1261-1274. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19462098>

